

Digital tools and technologies: Irish sheep stakeholder opinions before and after training

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Sm@RT, an EU Horizon 2020 funded project, aims to improve the understanding, awareness and uptake of digital tools and technologies available to small ruminant farmers. To facilitate this, each of the 8 participating countries (Estonia, France, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Norway, UK) hosted training days on farms. Training days consisted of workshops where stakeholders had a demonstration and opportunity to use digital tools/technologies. In Ireland, 3 training days were held where stakeholders were able to evaluate and use a variety of tools including Electronic Identification (EID) readers, EID weighcrate with autosorter, flock managements apps, sheep conveyor, lambing cameras and weather stations. Prior to and after each individual demonstration, stakeholders completed a short survey on their opinion of the tool or technology. After training, some of the stakeholders' opinions changed due to a better understanding of how to use the tool and learning about the potential benefits for their farms. Training days provided an opportunity for stakeholders to have hands-on experience and improve their understanding of the potential benefits of technologies/tools available to small ruminant farmers.